

**1-BAĞDAR: KÁNSHILIK TARAWÍNDÁ ÓNDRISTEGI EKOLÓGIYALÍQ,
EKONOMIKALÍQ, SOCIAL HÁM DE XIMIYA TEXNÓLOGIYASÍNÍN AKTUAL
MASHQALALARÍ**

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF MINING MACHINES

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Abstract: Mining dump trucks are specialized vehicles used in the mining and construction industries to transport large volumes of materials at quarries and construction sites. They have high load capacity and productivity, which allows you to efficiently move rocks, soil, sand and other materials.

Keyword: Control system, Maintenance and Condition, Engine, Engine Efficiency

The performance of dump trucks is determined by several factors, such as load capacity, travel speed and loading and unloading cycle times. Depending on the model and characteristics of the dump truck, its performance may vary.

Important parameters for assessing the performance of dump trucks include body capacity, engine power, transmission efficiency, driving resistance and other factors. Optimal performance is achieved by proper operation and maintenance of the dump truck.

Dump trucks play an important role in improving the efficiency and productivity of mining operations by providing reliable and efficient transportation of materials at mining sites.

The effectiveness of a dump truck is determined by its ability to perform cargo transportation tasks with the highest efficiency and productivity. Here are some factors that affect the efficiency of a dump truck:

Load Capacity: The greater the load capacity of a dump truck, the more materials or cargo it can transport in one cycle, which increases its productivity.

Travel speed: The fast travel speed of a dump truck allows it to quickly deliver cargo to the desired points and reduces transportation cycle time.

Engine Efficiency: A powerful and efficient engine allows the dump truck to overcome slopes and terrain obstacles with minimal fuel consumption.

Control system: Modern dump trucks are equipped with advanced control systems that optimize loading, unloading and maneuvering processes, which increases their efficiency.

Maintenance and Condition: Regular maintenance and maintaining your dump truck in good technical condition helps prevent unscheduled stops and reduces downtime, which affects its overall efficiency.

Dump trucks play an important role in the mining industry, providing efficient and reliable transportation of materials at mining sites. Their performance depends on factors such as load capacity, travel speed, engine efficiency, control system and maintenance.

To achieve maximum efficiency of dump trucks, it is recommended to choose models with optimal characteristics, carry out regular maintenance and maintain them in good technical condition. Optimizing loading, unloading and maneuvering processes can also improve the efficiency of dump trucks.

Overall, dump trucks are an integral part of the mining industry, helping to improve the productivity and efficiency of mining operations.

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QORAQALPOG'ISTON TABIIY RESURSLARINING XUDUDLARDA JOYLASHGANLIGI VA ULARDAN MINERAL XOMASHYOLARNING OLINISHI.

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